

Sufes Conjecture: a parameterized generalization of the Syracuse/Collatz conjecture

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Abstract

We study a family of arithmetic transformations on the integers, parameterized by a prime number k and two parameters (i, j) , which generalizes the Syracuse/Collatz-type iteration. The goal of this document is to establish structured conjectures — and, when possible, rigorous mathematical results — about observed quantities: division frequencies, stopping times, size and cardinality of cycles, mixing properties of residues, coalescence, and "footprint" phenomena (quasi-continuous exploration of the state space). Two special parameter regimes ($k = i = j$ and $k = i, j = 0$) are analyzed rigorously by induction: the first yields global divergence for all initial values, while the second produces a stable 2-cycle on the kernel ($n < k$) and divergence outside it. These results serve as concrete witnesses of the kernel's role in dictating global dynamics. A nonlinear generalization of the family is also introduced. This document consolidates the work carried out on this family of transformations, clarifies the definitions and the computational methodology, and proposes several paths toward formalization.

1 Introduction

Brief historical context.

The $3n + 1$ conjecture was formulated in the 1930s and is often attributed to Lothar Collatz (hence the name "Collatz conjecture"). It is also known as the "Syracuse conjecture" in the French literature, or the " $3x + 1$ problem". Despite its simplicity, it resists classical techniques in number theory and discrete dynamics. It has inspired notable contributions, including surveys by J. C. Lagarias, and probabilistic and ergodic advances; more recently, T. Tao obtained in 2019 an "almost all" result on the average decay of orbits. These works highlight the central role of this conjecture as a test problem in arithmetic dynamics.

The Syracuse conjecture rests on a simple definition: take a nonzero natural integer n and apply a series of operations (a transformation):

$$T_2(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2} & \text{if } n \text{ is even,} \\ 3n + 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The conjecture states that for any nonzero integer n , this transformation converges to a cycle $(1, 2, 4)$. If we look closely at the transformation, we notice that it relies on three main factors that favor convergence:

1. the transformation forces divisibility by 2 at the multiplication step (n odd $\Rightarrow 3n + 1$ even).
2. the condition is based on divisibility by a prime number (2).
3. the probability of hitting a number divisible by a power of 2 is large (the probability that an even number is divisible by 4 is $1/2$, for instance), which makes the probability that "the number of divisions is larger than the number of multiplications" significant, thus favoring convergence.

We can write the transformation as:

$$T_2(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2} & \text{if } 2 \mid n, \\ (2 + 1)n + (n \bmod 2) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Scope and status of this work. This manuscript is exploratory and conjectural. It does *not* present a proof of the classical Collatz/Syracuse conjecture, nor a proof of convergence for the generalized family introduced here. The results are based on heuristics, structural observations, and numerical experimentation, and should be interpreted as conjectures and empirical patterns rather than theorems.

2 Model and definition of the transformation

2.1 Definition of $T_{k,i,j}$

Let k be a prime number, $i \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}$ and $j \in \mathbb{N}$.

We define the transformation $T_{k,i,j} : \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^*$ by

$$T_{k,i,j}(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{k} & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{k}, \\ (k+i)n + (jk-i)(n \bmod k) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Convention (residue) : for $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$ we denote $r = n \bmod k \in \{0, 1, \dots, k-1\}$ the Euclidean residue.

Remark 1. *The parameter i may be any nonzero integer. Positive values of i are the focus of the stability analysis and the main conjecture. Negative values of i yield a contracting multiplier $k+i < k$ and are studied experimentally; the stability condition and sub-conjectures may require adaptation in that regime.*

2.2 Notation and trajectory

For a trajectory (n_t) we denote $r_t \equiv n_t \pmod{k}$ the residue at time t .

The valuation $v_k(n)$ (in the k -adic sense) is the largest integer $e \geq 0$ such that $k^e \mid n$ (with convention $v_k(0) = 0$ in the experimental metrics of the repository).

These quantities appear in several features (residues, distribution, Lyapunov, ...). For a fixed triplet (k, i, j) and an initial condition $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$:

- we define the trajectory by $n_{t+1} = T_{k,i,j}(n_t)$,
- we denote $\mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(n_0) = \{n_t : t \geq 0\}$ the orbit,
- we denote $r_t = n_t \bmod k$ the residue,
- we denote $v_k(n_t)$ the k -adic valuation of n_t ,
- we denote $\mathcal{C}_{k,i,j}(n_0)$ the cycle to which the transformation $T_{k,i,j}(n_0)$ converges.

2.3 Experimental environment

The "experimental" results explicitly refer to numerical limits.

Given the environment limitation, the following bounds are applied to all experiments (except a few punctual tests):

- $n \leq 10^7$
- $k \leq 47$
- A maximum divergence threshold of 10^{350} (beyond which the trajectory is considered divergent)
- A maximum number of iterations of 2×10^6 (beyond which the trajectory is considered divergent)

The Python code for the experiments is available on GitHub (see the Code and Data section near the end of this document).

3 Dynamic Stability

3.1 The stability condition

Exact (algebraic) result. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$ with $n = qk + r$, $r \neq 0$ (the case $r = 0$ is reduced to the previous case after a few divisions).

$$T_{k,i,j}(n) = (k+i)n + (jk-i)r = (k+i)(qk+r) + (jk-i)r = k[(k+i)q + (j+1)r].$$

This result is exact : whatever the parameters (k, i, j) and the integer n not divisible by k , we have $k \mid T_{k,i,j}(n)$, i.e. $v_k(T_{k,i,j}(n)) \geq 1$.

Heuristic analysis — expected valuation. *The results below rely on two unproven working hypotheses:*

1. *the contribution of the term $(j+1)r$ is negligible compared to $(k+i)q$ in the asymptotic estimate,*
2. *the values of $S_{k,i,j}(n) = (k+i)q + (j+1)r$ behave like "pseudo-random" integers modulo powers of k (hypothesis of k -adic equidistribution).*

These hypotheses are consistent with numerical experiments but are not rigorously established.

Let $S_{k,i,j}(n) = \frac{T_{k,i,j}(n)}{k} = (k+i)q + (j+1)r$. Since $0 < r < k$, we have $(j+1)r = O(k, j)$, and asymptotically:

$$S_{k,i,j}(n) = \frac{k+i}{k} n + O(k, j).$$

Under the k -adic equidistribution hypothesis on $S_{k,i,j}(n)$:

$$E[v_k(T_{k,i,j}(n))] = 1 + E[v_k(S_{k,i,j}(n))] \approx 1 + \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{m=0}^N \frac{(k-1)^m}{k^{m+1}} = 1 + \frac{1}{k-1} = \frac{k}{k-1}.$$

Contraction criterion (heuristic). The heuristic Lyapunov exponent of the transformation is:

$$\lambda = \ln\left(\frac{k+i}{k^{k/(k-1)}}\right).$$

Heuristically, the system is contracting when $\lambda < 0$, i.e.:

$$\boxed{i < k^{\frac{k}{k-1}} - k.}$$

Warning: this inequality is a necessary heuristic condition, not a proven sufficient condition. It does not account for the $O(k, j)$ terms nor possible resonance effects between parameters. In particular, for $i = 4$, the formula predicts a threshold around $k \approx 37$ – 41 , while experiments confirm stability starting at $k = 43$; this gap illustrates the margin of error of the asymptotic analysis.

Experiments (on $n \leq 10^7$, $k \leq 47$) show that the transformations are stable for the following values:

i	$\min(k)$
1	2
2	3
3	13
4	43

We note the following:

- i controls the system expansion and dictates stability/divergence.
- For $i = 1$, the transformation is stable for all primes k .
- The larger i becomes, the larger the minimal value of k , following an exponential law.
- j is not a constraining parameter on stability but a bounded effect that acts locally on orbits.

Remark: The results above are heuristic, and thus we set a theoretical bound (likely very restrictive) on j as follows: $0 \leq j \leq 2k$. It is difficult to determine a heuristic bound on the value of j .

The experimental results are provided with the companion repository.

Special case of stability.

Proposition 1 (Explicit periodic point for $i = 1$). *Let k be prime, $j \geq 1$, and consider $T_{k,1,j}$. For $n_0 = jk - 1$, the even iterates satisfy, for all $t \in \{0, \dots, k-2\}$:*

$$n_{2t} = (t+1)(jk-1).$$

In particular, $n_{2k-1} = n_0$, and the minimal period of n_0 is exactly $2k-1$.

Proof. For $t = 0$, $n_0 = jk-1$, so the formula holds. Assume $n_{2t} = (t+1)(jk-1)$ for some $t \in \{0, \dots, k-3\}$. Then

$$n_{2t} = ((t+1)j-1)k + (k-(t+1)),$$

hence $r_{2t} = k - (t+1) \in \{1, \dots, k-1\}$. Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} n_{2t+1} &= (k+1)n_{2t} + (jk-1)r_{2t} \\ &= (k+1)(t+1)(jk-1) + (jk-1)(k-t-1) \\ &= (jk-1)((k+1)(t+1) + k-t-1) \\ &= (t+2)k(jk-1), \end{aligned}$$

thus

$$n_{2t+2} = \frac{n_{2t+1}}{k} = (t+2)(jk-1).$$

The induction is complete. Taking $t = k-2$ gives $n_{2k-4} = (k-1)(jk-1)$, then

$$n_{2k-3} = k^2(jk-1), \quad n_{2k-2} = k(jk-1), \quad n_{2k-1} = jk-1 = n_0.$$

So n_0 is periodic with a period that divides $2k-1$.

It remains to prove minimality. Let $0 < s < 2k-1$.

- If $s = 2t$ is even, then necessarily $0 \leq t \leq k-1$ and $n_{2t} = (t+1)(jk-1)$. Since $jk-1 > 0$, we have $n_{2t} = n_0 \iff t+1 = 1 \iff t = 0$, hence no even index $2 \leq s \leq 2k-2$ returns to n_0 .
- If $s = 2t+1$ is odd, then n_{2t+1} is a multiple of k (because every odd step here is of the form $k \times \text{integer}$), while $n_0 = jk-1 \equiv -1 \pmod{k}$, so $k \nmid n_0$. Therefore $n_{2t+1} \neq n_0$ for all odd s .

Hence there is no return time s with $0 < s < 2k-1$, and the minimal period is exactly $2k-1$. \square

3.2 Instability samples

The following two propositions are proven by induction and illustrate how the choice of parameters can force global divergence or constrain the kernel to a periodic orbit. They serve as concrete witnesses of the kernel's role in dictating the behavior of the system.

Case $k = i = j$.

Proposition 2 (Divergence for $k = i = j$). *Let k be a prime and consider $T_{k,k,k}$. For any $n_0 = qk + r$ with $q \in \mathbb{N}$, $r \in \{0, \dots, k-1\}$, the even iterates satisfy, for all $t \geq 0$:*

$$n_{2t} = 2^t kq + (2^t - 1)kr + r.$$

In particular, for $r \neq 0$ (kernel elements if $q = 0$, or any n with $k \nmid n$), the sequence (n_{2t}) is unbounded, hence the trajectory diverges.

Proof. The formula holds for $t = 0$. Assume it holds for some $t \geq 0$. Then:

$$n_{2t+1} = T_{k,k,k}(n_{2t}) = (k+k)n_{2t} + (k^2 - k)r = k(2^{t+1}kq + (2^{t+1} - 1)kr + r),$$

so $n_{2t+2} = n_{2t+1}/k = 2^{t+1}kq + (2^{t+1} - 1)kr + r$, which is the formula at rank $t+1$. Since the coefficient of n in $n_{2t} = ((2^t - 1)k + 1)n$ (for $q = 0$) grows exponentially with t , the trajectory is unbounded. The case $r = 0$ reduces to a multiple of k , which after $\nu_k(n_0)$ divisions falls back into the $r \neq 0$ case (after $\nu_k(n_0)$ divisions). \square

Case $k = i$, $j = 0$.

Proposition 3 (Kernel 2-cycle and exterior divergence for $k = i$, $j = 0$). *Let k be a prime and consider $T_{k,k,0}$. For any $n_0 = qk + r$ with $q \in \mathbb{N}$, $r \in \{1, \dots, k-1\}$, the even iterates satisfy, for all $t \geq 0$:*

$$n_{2t} = 2^t kq + r.$$

Two distinct regimes follow:

- **Kernel** ($q = 0$): $n_{2t} = r = n_0$ for all t , so the orbit is the periodic 2-cycle $\{n_0, kn_0\}$.
- **Exterior** ($q \geq 1$): $n_{2t} \rightarrow +\infty$, so the trajectory diverges.

Proof. The formula holds for $t = 0$. Assume it holds for some $t \geq 0$. Then:

$$n_{2t+1} = T_{k,k,0}(n_{2t}) = (k+k)n_{2t} + (0 \cdot k - k)r = 2kn_{2t} - kr = k(2^{t+1}kq + r),$$

where $2kn_{2t} - kr = k(2n_{2t} - r) > 0$ since $n_{2t} \geq r$ (as $n_{2t} = 2^t kq + r \geq r$). Hence $n_{2t+2} = k(2^{t+1}kq + r)/k = 2^{t+1}kq + r$, closing the induction. For $q = 0$ the formula gives $n_{2t} = r$ (constant), confirming the 2-cycle. For $q \geq 1$ the term $2^t kq$ grows without bound. \square

Remark 2. *These two propositions highlight contrasting kernel behaviors: $T_{k,k,k}$ forces unbounded growth even on the kernel, while $T_{k,k,0}$ traps kernel elements in a stable 2-cycle but causes all exterior orbits to diverge. Both cases confirm that the dynamics of the kernel ($n < k$) are central to the global behavior of the system.*

3.3 Cycles

3.3.1 Finiteness of cycles

Under the stability condition (i.e. ultimate convergence), let $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$. By definition, $\mathcal{C}_{k,i,j}(n) \subset \mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(n)$.

Finiteness. If convergence is proved, then the orbit $\mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(n)$ is ultimately periodic. The periodic part is a cycle, hence finite. Thus,

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^* : \quad \text{card}(\mathcal{C}_{k,i,j}(n)) < \infty.$$

Uniform boundedness (not deduced). Convergence does not imply the existence of a uniform bound on cycle sizes. The statement

$$\exists c_{k,i,j} \forall n \in \mathbb{N}^* : \text{card}(\mathcal{C}_{k,i,j}(n)) \leq c_{k,i,j}$$

is a stronger property, which we formulate as a distinct conjecture. Numerical experiments suggest cycles of moderate size, but do not rule out rare cycles of arbitrarily large size.

Numerical experiments strongly suggest that observed cycles remain of moderate size.

However, the possible existence of exceptional cycles appearing at arbitrarily large scales cannot be excluded.

Thus, proving the finiteness of the total number of cycles per combination (k, i, j) seems to be a problem essentially as hard as establishing global convergence of the system.

3.3.2 Extra Special Cycles

Experiments show that, for some combinations (k, i, j) , the transformation lands on the same cycle for all nonzero integers n (a global attractor).

We call a cycle unique per combination an "extra special cycle" and we note: $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*; \mathcal{C}_{k,i,j}(n) = \mathcal{C}_{k,i,j}(1)$.

Examples:

1. The first example, the classical Syracuse/Collatz transformation ($k = 2, i = 1, j = 1$):

$$T_{2,1,1}(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2} & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ 3n + 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*; \mathcal{C}_{2,1,1}(n) = \mathcal{C}_{2,1,1}(1) = (4, 2, 1).$$

2. Another example, still for $k = 2$ ($k = 2, i = 1, j = 2$):

$$T_{2,1,2}(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2} & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ 3n + 3 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*; \mathcal{C}_{2,1,2}(n) = \mathcal{C}_{2,1,2}(1) = (6, 3, 12).$$

3. Another example, with prime $k = 5$ ($k = 5, i = 1, j = 1$):

$$T_{5,1,1}(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{5} & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \\ 6n + 4r & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*; \mathcal{C}_{5,1,1}(n) = \mathcal{C}_{5,1,1}(1) = (4, 40, 8, 60, 12, 80, 16, 100, 20).$$

4. $k = 11$ ($k = 11, i = 1, j = 3$):

$$T_{11,1,3}(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{11} & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{11}, \\ 12n + 32r & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*; \mathcal{C}_{11,1,3}(n) = \mathcal{C}_{11,1,3}(1) = (32, 704, 64, 1056, 96, 1408, 128, 1760, 160, 2112, 192, 2464, 224, 2816, 256, 3168, 288, 3520, 320, 3872, 352).$$

5. $k = 43$ ($k = 43, i = 1, j = 3$):

$$T_{43,1,3}(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{43} & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{43}, \\ 44n + 128r & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*; \mathcal{C}_{43,1,3}(n) = \mathcal{C}_{43,1,3}(1) = (128, 11008, 256, 16512, 384, 22016, 512, 27520, 640, 33024, 768, 38528, 896, 44032, 1024, 49536, 1152, 55040, 1280, 60544, 1408, 66048, 1536, 71552, 1664, 77056, 1792, 82560, 1920, 88064, 2048, 93568, 2176, 99072, 2304, 104576, 2432, 110080, 2560, 115584, 2688, 121088, 2816, 126592, 2944, 132096, 3072, 137600, 3200, 143104, 3328, 148608, 3456, 154112, 3584, 159616, 3712, 165120, 3840, 170624, 3968, 176128, 4096, 181632, 4224, 187136, 4352, 192640, 4480, 198144, 4608, 203648, 4736, 209152, 4864, 214656, 4992, 220160, 5120, 225664, 5248, 231168, 5376, 236672, 5504)$

By the previous proposition, for $i = 1$ and $j \geq 1$, the point $n_0 = jk - 1$ is periodic with minimal period $2k - 1$. In combinations exhibiting an Extra Special Cycle, this implies that the unique cycle is the orbit of $n_0 = jk - 1$ and has cardinality exactly $2k - 1$.

3.3.3 Special Cycles

Some other combinations converge to several cycles but with the same size. We call this type of cycles "special cycles". In other words: $\exists c \geq 2; \forall n \in \mathbb{N}^*; \text{card}(\mathcal{C}_{k,i,j}(n)) = c$.

Examples:

- $(k = 7, i = 1, j = 0) \Rightarrow c = 2$:
 $\mathcal{C}_{7,1,0}(n) \in \{(1, 7), (2, 14), (3, 21), (4, 28), (5, 35), (6, 42)\}$
- $(k = 11, i = 1, j = 0) \Rightarrow c = 2$:
 $\mathcal{C}_{11,1,0}(n) \in \{(1, 11), (2, 22), (3, 33), (4, 44), (5, 55), (6, 66), (7, 77), (8, 88), (9, 99), (10, 110)\}$
- $(k = 17, i = 1, j = 0) \Rightarrow c = 2$:
 $\mathcal{C}_{17,1,0}(n) \in \{(1, 17), (2, 34), (3, 51), (4, 68), (5, 85), (6, 102), (7, 119), (8, 136), (9, 153), (10, 170), (11, 187), (12, 204), (13, 221), (14, 238), (15, 255), (16, 272)\}$
- $(k = 29, i = 1, j = 0) \Rightarrow c = 2$:
 $\mathcal{C}_{29,1,0}(n) \in \{(1, 29), (2, 58), (3, 87), (4, 116), (5, 145), (6, 174), (7, 203), (8, 232), (9, 261), (10, 290), (11, 319), (12, 348), (13, 377), (14, 406), (15, 435), (16, 464), (17, 493), (18, 522), (19, 551), (20, 580), (21, 609), (22, 638), (23, 667), (24, 696), (25, 725), (26, 754), (27, 783), (28, 812)\}$

We can observe that for these combinations, the cycle size is always 2 ($c = 2$), the number and content are dictated by the orbits of the numbers $n \in \{1, \dots, k - 1\}$, but this does not suggest that it is a general rule (the combination $(k = 3, i = 1, j = 0)$ is a counterexample).

3.3.4 Stratigraphy

We denote $c_{min}(n) = \min(\mathcal{C}_{k,i,j}(n))$ the points that represent the first occurrences of the different cycles. We notice that the curve representing these points follows a law close to $\frac{1}{n}$.

Globally, from the study of these two types of cycles and their first occurrences, we can create a kind of dynamic stratigraphy that organizes the phase space into 3 layers:

1. The core (kernel):

This is the zone where stable structures are born. The behavior of the transformation for numbers $n = r \in \{1, \dots, k - 1\}$ will determine globally (and sometimes exactly) the shape, the cardinality and the number of cycles. It will thus determine globally the behavior for the rest of the numbers n . And these numbers will form a kind of basin that will capture the majority (or all) of the space. The cycles created by this core will cover, at least, the cycles of all numbers that can be written as $n = rk^m; r \in \{1, \dots, k - 1\}; m \in \mathbb{N}^*$, by definition of the transformation $T_{k,i,j}(n)$.

2. The critical boundary N_{crit} :

There would exist a number N_{crit} such that the second layer $n \in \{k, \dots, N_{crit}\}$ complements the

behavior with a few new cycles, to ultimately describe almost the entire space. N_{crit} represents a saturation horizon.

3. The periphery:

Beyond N_{crit} , the probability of discovering a new cycle collapses. The processing of numbers $n > N_{crit}$ is purely transient. Their trajectories are logarithmic erosions until they reach one of the two previous layers (at some point the trajectory of n will coalesce with the trajectory of a number that belongs to the core layer, or the critical boundary layer).

We also note that varying the parameter j for a fixed prime k can strongly change the global structure of trajectories. One can move from a combination with an extra-special cycle to a combination with special cycles, or even to a combination with chaotic cycles.

Figure 1: Three-layer stratigraphy

3.4 Probability of deep valuations

Divisibility by powers of primes is at the core of this family of transformations. In this part we study the characteristics of this divisibility.

Let n be a nonzero natural integer and let (n_m) be its orbit under $T_{k,i,j}$. Recall that each multiplication step produces a number divisible by k , more precisely by a power of k .

We define the coefficient $A_v(n)$ as the ratio of the number of multiplication operations producing numbers divisible by k^2 (or more) to the total number of multiplications:

$$A_v(n) = \frac{\#\{\text{multiplications giving } v_k \geq 2\}}{\#\{\text{multiplications}\}} = P(v_k(T_{k,i,j}(n)) \geq 2 \mid k \nmid n).$$

Heuristic estimate. *The following estimate relies on the k -adic equidistribution hypothesis: we assume that the results of multiplicative steps behave like integers drawn uniformly modulo k^m . This hypothesis is not proven; it is motivated by the analogy with pseudo-random models of Collatz-type iterations.*

Under this hypothesis:

$$A_v \approx P(v_k \geq 2) = \frac{1}{k}.$$

Experiments confirm that $A_v(n)$ is very close to $\frac{1}{k}$, with a slight dependence on j :

$$A_v = \frac{1}{k} + o(k, j).$$

This formula is a heuristic result validated experimentally, not an established analytic identity.

A2 = P(v_k(next)≥2 | multiplication) (n=10000, p=47), j_mult=2

Figure 2: A_v mean value per k, j for $i = 2, k \in \{3..47\}, 0 \leq j \leq 2k$

3.5 Density of divisions

Let n be a nonzero natural integer and let (n_m) be its orbit under $T_{k,i,j}$. Each multiplication step produces a result divisible by a power of k .

We define $A_0(n)$ as the asymptotic density of division operations in the orbit:

$$A_0(n) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=0}^{N-1} \mathbf{1}_{k|n_t}.$$

We denote $v_{\max}(n) = \max_{m \geq 0} v_k(n_m)$ the maximum k -adic valuation reached along the orbit.

Derivation under a heuristic hypothesis. *The formula below is obtained under the **pseudo-uniform k -adic hypothesis**: we assume that, conditionally on $k \mid n_t$, the valuation $v_k(n_t)$ follows the truncated geometric law $P(v \geq m \mid v \geq 1) = k^{-(m-1)}$. This hypothesis models a pseudo-random behavior of valuations; it is not proven analytically but is consistent with numerical simulations.*

We split the orbit into blocks: each block is composed of a multiplication followed by $v = v_k(T_{k,i,j}(n))$ consecutive divisions. Hence:

$$A_0(n) = \frac{E[v]}{E[v] + 1}.$$

Under the pseudo-uniform k -adic hypothesis:

$$E[v] = \sum_{m=1}^{v_{\max}(n)} P(v \geq m \mid v \geq 1) = \sum_{m=1}^{v_{\max}(n)} \frac{1}{k^{m-1}} = \frac{k}{k-1} (1 - k^{-v_{\max}(n)}).$$

Substituting:

$$A_0(n) = \frac{k - k^{1-v_{\max}(n)}}{2k - 1 - k^{1-v_{\max}(n)}}.$$

This expression is a heuristic result; its exact value depends on the validity of the equidistribution hypothesis.

Interpretation.

- We verify that $A_0(n) > \frac{1}{2}$, and $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} A_0(n) = \frac{1}{2}$: the number of divisions slightly exceeds the number of multiplications, which is consistent with the heuristic contraction of the trajectory.
- Experiments suggest that $v_{\max}(n) \rightarrow 2$ when $k \rightarrow \infty$: divisibility by large powers of k becomes very rare. For large k , the heuristic estimate simplifies to:

$$A_0 \approx \frac{k^2 - 1}{2k^2 - k - 1} = \frac{k + 1}{2k + 1}.$$

This approximation is asymptotically valid in k under the hypothesis $v_{\max} = 2$, itself unproven.

Figure 3: A_0 mean value, per k, j for $i = 1, k \in \{2..47\}, 0 \leq j \leq 2k$

3.6 Residue distribution

The analysis of residue distribution along orbits will focus on nonzero residues. Recall that the ratio of zero residues (states n_t divisible by k) is expressed by the value of A_0 . The nonzero residues are $\{1, \dots, k-1\}$. If these residues are uniformly distributed, then:

$$P(r = a) = \frac{1}{k-1} \Rightarrow E(r) = \frac{1}{k-1} \sum_{a=1}^{k-1} a = \frac{1}{k-1} \frac{k(k-1)}{2} = \frac{k}{2}$$

In experiments, we see that this expectation is very close to this value, which shows that the residues are

not perfectly equidistributed. The exception is $k = 2$, where $E(r) = \frac{1}{2}$ since there is only one residue: 1. Let us now look at the standard deviation of nonzero residues: $V(r) = E(r^2) - (E(r))^2$, but $E(r^2) = \frac{1}{k-1} \sum_{a=1}^{k-1} a^2 = \frac{k(2k-1)}{6}$
 $V(r) = \frac{k(2k-1)}{6} - \frac{k^2}{4} = \frac{k(k-2)}{12} \Rightarrow \sigma_r = \sqrt{\frac{k(k-2)}{12}}$
 When k is large, we have $\sigma_r \approx \frac{k-1}{2\sqrt{3}}$.

Figure 4: σ_r Residues Standard Deviation per k, j for $i = 2, k \in \{3, \dots, 47\}, 0 \leq j \leq 2k$

Interpretation:

Although the nonzero residues are not equidistributed, their low-order statistical moments seem to converge to those of the uniform law on $\{1, \dots, k-1\}$.

3.7 Stopping Time

We define the **Stopping Time** as the minimal number of iterations before the trajectory drops strictly below the initial value:

$$\sigma_{k,i,j}(n) = \min\{t \geq 1 : n_t < n\}.$$

Heuristic estimate. *The following estimate is heuristic: it assumes that the $2k$ operations of the average resistance (SC5) succeed one another without perturbation from the $O(k, j)$ term, and that the asymptotic behavior of $\left(\frac{k+1}{k}\right)^k \rightarrow e$ is reached as early as $t = 2k + 1$. These assumptions hold on average but do not constitute a proof for each individual n .*

For $i = 1$, after $2k$ alternating operations (multiplication/division), the contribution of the growth factor accumulates as follows:

$$n_{2k+1} \approx \left(\frac{k+1}{k}\right)^k \frac{n}{k} \approx \frac{e}{k} n < n.$$

The contribution of the parameter j slightly delays the descent. We deduce the heuristic approximation:

$$\sigma_{k,i,j}(n) \approx 2k + 1 + \lfloor O(k, j) \rfloor.$$

This formula is an order-of-magnitude estimate, not an exact equality. The precise value of $\sigma_{k,i,j}(n)$ depends on the residues encountered along the trajectory and can vary significantly around this average.

Special case. For some combinations (k, i, j) , certain integers n satisfy $n_T = n$ (exact return to the starting value): this means n belongs directly to a cycle, i.e. $\mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(n) = \mathcal{C}_{k,i,j}(n)$. Observed examples:

$$T_{3,1,0}(22), \quad T_{5,1,0}(57), \quad T_{7,1,1}(89), \quad T_{17,1,16}(271), \quad \dots$$

3.8 The Footprint phenomenon

To study the **arithmetic dynamics** of the transformation, we define a **contiguous global attractor** called the Continuous Footprint $f_{k,i,j}(n)$.

Let $\mathcal{F}_{k,i,j}(n) = \bigcup_{m=1}^n \mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(m)$ be the union of the orbits of all numbers less than or equal to n . We call $\mathcal{F}_{k,i,j}(n)$ the global footprint of n and it represents the spatial diffusion of the transformation $T_{k,i,j}(n)$. Let $I_n = [1, f_{k,i,j}(n)]$ be the largest interval of consecutive integers (with no gaps) contained in \mathcal{F}_n (the Continuous Footprint $f_{k,i,j}(n)$ of n is the boundary of the interval).

Experiments have shown that $f_{k,i,j}(n)$ does not deviate too far from n .

In general: $f_{k,i,j}(n) = n + o(n, k, j)$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f_{k,i,j}(n)}{n} = 1$

A special case is the following:

$$j = 1; k \geq 3 \Rightarrow f_{k,i,j}(n) = n + n \bmod 2$$

This shows that, in general, $n + 1 \notin I_n$; even if the system is stable for all integers $\leq n$, stability for $n + 1$ is not systematic.

In the same way, we observe that:

$$\mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(n+1) \cap \mathcal{F}_{k,i,j}(n) \neq \emptyset \text{ and,}$$

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\mathcal{F}_{k,i,j}(n)}{n} = \alpha(k, j)$ where $\alpha(k, j)$ is a very small value.

$\alpha(k, j)$ represents the average number of new states visited per expansion step.

We recall that, in Section 3.3.4, we defined a 3-layer stratigraphy, namely: Core, Critical Boundary, Periphery.

This stratigraphy explains the trend behavior of $\mathcal{F}_{k,i,j}(n)$ and is validated by the value of $\alpha(k, j)$.

Since the majority (or all) of the cycles are discovered at values either $\leq k$ or $\leq N_{crit}$, beyond these values the new orbits $\mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(n)$ will not visit too many new values, and will quickly coalesce with $\mathcal{F}_{k,i,j}(n-1)$.

3.9 Coalescence

To complement the work on the Continuous Footprint, in this section we study the coalescence of the orbit of n ($\mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(n)$) with the orbits of numbers less than n . Numerical experiments allowed us to define a coalescence ratio $C_{k,i,j}$ as follows:

$$C_{k,i,j} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\#\{n \leq N : \exists m < n, \mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(n) \cap \mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(m) \neq \emptyset\}}{N} \quad (1)$$

We observe that:

$$\frac{\#\{n \leq N : \exists m < n, \mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(n) \cap \mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(m) \neq \emptyset\}}{N} = 1 + o(k, i, j), \text{ and } C_{k,i,j} = 1$$

This behavior is consistent with the 3-layer dynamic stratigraphy (Core, Critical Boundary, Periphery). The majority of cycles are generated by numbers $n \leq N_{crit}$; the rest of the numbers coalesce with these, except for a few exceptions that create their own arithmetic highways and cycles.

In the special case of combinations k, i, j with Extra Special Cycles, the ratio is always constant:

$$\frac{\#\{n \leq N : \exists m < n, \mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(n) \cap \mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(m) \neq \emptyset\}}{N} = 1$$

We also study in this part the mean coalescence time (mean Capture Time) $T_{k,i,j}$ which represents the average number of operations until the orbit of n is captured by $\mathcal{F}_{k,i,j}(n-1)$.

3.10 Resistance dynamics and geometric law

Given the importance of divisibility by a power of k , we define the **resistance** of the transformation $T_{k,i,j}(n)$ as the average number of multiplication and division operations (M,D,M,D,M,D,...) before hitting a first number multiple of k^m , $m \geq 2$.

Let $v_t = v_k(n_t)$ during multiplicative steps.

Since $n_t \equiv 0 \pmod{k}$ during these steps, we have $v_t \geq 1$.

As long as $v_t = 1$, the system will continue to alternate division and multiplication operations (D,M,D,M,D,M,...).

The resistance "breaks" as soon as we hit $v_t \geq 2$.

We reuse the definition of operation blocks but this time with blocks of exact size 2: (M,D) (or (D,M) depending on the first iteration of processing a number n).

We define: $\tau = \min\{t \geq 1; v_t \geq 2\}$ the number of critical blocks before break.

Under the conditional pseudo-uniform hypothesis:

$$P(v_t \geq m | v_t \geq 1) = \frac{1}{k^{m-1}}$$

So, the break probability is:

$$P(v_t \geq 2) = \frac{1}{k}$$

And, the resistance probability:

$$P(v_t = 1) = 1 - P(v_t \geq 2) = 1 - \frac{1}{k} = \frac{k-1}{k}$$

To resist for exactly m blocks, we need: $v_1 = 1, v_2 = 1, \dots, v_{m-1} = 1, v_m \geq 2$.

$$P(\tau = m) = \left(\frac{k-1}{k}\right)^{m-1} \frac{1}{k}$$

$E[\tau] = \sum_{m \geq 1} mP(\tau = m) = \sum_{m \geq 1} m \left(\frac{k-1}{k}\right)^{m-1} \frac{1}{k} = \frac{1}{k} \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{k-1}{k}\right)^2} = k$ Given that the size of resistance blocks is

2, we have: $R = 2 * E[\tau] = 2k$

Interpretation:

On average, for any natural integer n , the transformation $T_{k,i,j}(n)$ performs $2k$ operations before hitting a number multiple of k^m , $m \geq 2$.

3.11 Trajectories

A trajectory (n_t) of n is the sequence representing the set of points visited by n in the form $n_{t+1} = T_{k,i,j}(n_t)$.

The key parameters of this dynamical system (cycles, deep valuations, division density, stopping time, footprint and coalescence) make this trajectory a series of exponential sawtooth growths with sporadic sharp drops (which correspond to deep k -adic valuations $v_k(n_t) \geq 2$).

Example:

Figure 5: Trajectory for $n = 1270, k = 11, i = 2, j = 4$

The minimal value of the trajectory is that of the cycle: $\min((n_t)_t) = \min(C_{k,i,j}(n))$.

We also note: $\min((n_t)_t) \leq n$.

3.12 Formulation of the Sufes conjecture

The set of results presented in this document allows us to describe the family $\{T_{k,i,j}\}$ as a **discrete arithmetic dynamical system**, whose global behavior is governed by a set of structural laws. We group them here in the form of a main conjecture and several sub-conjectures.

The name "Sufes" is given to this family in reference to Sufes, an ancient Roman city (the current city is my hometown); see <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sufes>.

Main conjecture (Sufes). *Let k be a prime number and $(i, j) \in \mathbb{N}^* \times \mathbb{N}$ such that*

$$i < k^{\frac{k}{k-1}} - k.$$

Then for all $n \in \mathbb{N}^$, the orbit $\mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(n)$ is ultimately periodic: there exist $T \geq 0$ and $p \geq 1$ such that $n_{T+p} = n_T$. In other words, the transformation $T_{k,i,j}$ is globally convergent on \mathbb{N}^* .*

The heuristic results of the previous sections refine the fine structure of this convergence. They are formulated below as independent sub-conjectures, each experimentally tested on $n \leq 10^7$ and $k \leq 47$.

Sub-conjecture 1 (Finiteness and boundedness of cycles). *Under the stability condition, all cycles are finite, and their cardinality is uniformly bounded in n :*

$$\exists c_{k,i,j} \in \mathbb{N}^*, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}^* : \text{card}(\mathcal{C}_{k,i,j}(n)) \leq c_{k,i,j}.$$

Sub-conjecture 2 (Density of divisions A_0). *The asymptotic density of division operations in any orbit satisfies:*

$$A_0(n) = \frac{k - k^{1-v_{\max}(n)}}{2k - 1 - k^{1-v_{\max}(n)}},$$

with $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} A_0 = \frac{k+1}{2k+1}$. In particular $A_0 > \frac{1}{2}$, which guarantees the mean contraction of the trajectory.

Sub-conjecture 3 (Probability of deep valuations A_v). *The probability that a multiplication step produces a multiple of k^2 satisfies:*

$$A_v = P(v_k(T_{k,i,j}(n)) \geq 2 \mid k \nmid n) = \frac{1}{k} + o(k, j),$$

consistent with the pseudo-uniform k -adic hypothesis on the results of multiplicative steps.

Sub-conjecture 4 (Residue distribution). *On a generic orbit, the nonzero residues $r_t = n_t \bmod k \in \{1, \dots, k-1\}$ are asymptotically nearly uniformly distributed. Their moments converge to those of the uniform law on $\{1, \dots, k-1\}$:*

$$E[r] \approx \frac{k}{2}, \quad \sigma_r \approx \sqrt{\frac{k(k-2)}{12}} \underset{k \rightarrow \infty}{\sim} \frac{k}{2\sqrt{3}}.$$

Sub-conjecture 5 (Resistance and geometric law, $R = 2k$). *The number of (M, D) blocks before a valuation $v_k \geq 2$ occurs follows a geometric law with parameter $1/k$. The mean resistance is:*

$$R = 2 E[\tau] = 2k.$$

Sub-conjecture 6 (Stopping Time). *The minimal number of operations to drop below the initial value satisfies:*

$$\sigma_{k,i,j}(n) = 2k + 1 + \lfloor O(k, j) \rfloor,$$

where the term $O(k, j)$ accounts for the contribution of parameter j . This result follows from:

$$n_{2k+1} \approx \left(\frac{k+1}{k}\right)^k \frac{n}{k} \approx \frac{e}{k} n < n.$$

Sub-conjecture 7 (Universal coalescence). *The coalescence ratio is maximal:*

$$C_{k,i,j} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\#\{n \leq N : \exists m < n, \mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(n) \cap \mathcal{O}_{k,i,j}(m) \neq \emptyset\}}{N} = 1.$$

This phenomenon is a direct consequence of the three-layer stratigraphy (core, critical boundary, periphery): beyond N_{crit} , every new orbit coalesces with an earlier orbit.

Sub-conjecture 8 (Continuous Footprint). *The global footprint $f_{k,i,j}(n)$ satisfies:*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f_{k,i,j}(n)}{n} = 1,$$

and the marginal expansion ratio $\alpha(k, j) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} |\mathcal{F}_{k,i,j}(n)|/n$ is a very small constant that decreases with k .

Synthesis. These eight sub-conjectures together form a coherent portrait of $T_{k,i,j}$ as a dynamical system:

- **Contraction** (SC2) ensures the average decay of trajectories.
- **Mixing** (SC3, SC4) guarantees the absence of residual trapping.
- **Rhythm** (SC5, SC6) quantifies the descent speed.
- **Attraction** (SC7, SC8) describes the global convergence of the phase space toward a finite set of cycles (SC1).

The main Sufes conjecture is thus the global result that follows, heuristically, from the simultaneous coherence of all these properties.

3.13 k -periodic spiral representation

We can imagine k as a periodicity (equivalent to 2π). Given that we can write $n_t = ak+r; r \in \{0, \dots, k-1\}$ for all points visited by the trajectory of n until reaching a cycle.

Geometrically we may think of a as the radius and r/k as the angle.

To make the rendering displayable, we define:

- The angle: $n_t \frac{2\pi}{k}$
- The radius: $\ln(\lfloor n_t \rfloor + 1)$ (to keep the scale readable for large values)

The trajectory representation yields a rendering that follows the axes $\frac{2\pi r}{k}; r \in \{0, \dots, k-1\}$:

Spirale $n=123456789$ $p=97$ $i=1$ $j=1$ (angle=step)

Figure 6: Spiral representation for $n = 123456789, i = 1, j = 1, k \in \{2..97\}$

4 Generalization of the family of transformations

4.1 Nonlinear example

Let the following transformation be defined for all $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$; $i \in \mathbb{N}^*$; $j \in \mathbb{N}$; k a prime number and $m \in \mathbb{N}^*$. We define the transformation:

$$T_{k,i,j}(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{k} & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{k}, \\ (k + (-m)^n i) n + (jk - (-m)^n i) (n \bmod k) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

This family of transformations "alternates" according to the parity of n_t , and by definition it behaves very similarly to the family of transformations defined in the previous section.

Trajectory example:

Figure 7: Alternated trajectory for $n = 1273, k = 11, i = 2, j = 4, m = 1$

The stability condition will now depend on the value of k and m . We also suggest that the various structures (cycles, residue distribution, resistance, stopping time, ...) will have an additional dependence on m .

4.2 Generalization

In general, one can define a family parameterized by arithmetic functions $f, g : \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ (with k prime):

$$T_{k,f,g}(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{k} & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{k}, \\ f(k)n + g(k)(n \bmod k) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Divisibility condition. Writing $n = qk + r$ with $r \in \{1, \dots, k-1\}$, we obtain

$$T_{k,f,g}(n) = f(k)qk + (f(k) + g(k))r.$$

Thus, to ensure $k \mid T_{k,f,g}(n)$ for all $n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{k}$, it is sufficient (and necessary) that

$$k \mid f(k) + g(k).$$

This condition is the general counterpart of the structural constraint of the model $T_{k,i,j}$.

Also we have:

$$\frac{T_{k,f,g}(n)}{k} = f(k)q + \frac{(f(k) + g(k))}{k}r.$$

f acts on the multiplier, thus defines the condition for stability.

Whereas, $\frac{f(k)+g(k)}{k}$ acts on the residus as a local factor, defining the structure of different aspects of the transformation (cycles, Coalescence, Resistance, Stopping Time, ...)

Link with the family $T_{k,i,j}$. The initial model corresponds to the choice

$$f(k) = k + i, \quad g(k) = jk - i,$$

for which $f(k) + g(k) = (j + 1)k$, hence divisibility is automatic.

$\frac{f(k)+g(k)}{k} = j + 1$, hence the parameter j is controlling the local behaviour of the transformation.

Comments. Studying stability for arbitrary choices of f and g seems out of reach without additional hypotheses (controlled growth of f , pseudo-random behavior of residues, etc.). This generalization highlights the need to clearly formalize notions of stability, convergence and cycles before expecting rigorous results.

5 Conclusion

This document presented and studied the family of transformations $T_{k,i,j}$, a parameterized generalization of the Syracuse/Collatz conjecture. We established heuristic stability conditions, characterized the different types of cycles (Extra Special, Special, and chaotic), and described the key dynamic properties: density of divisions, residue distribution, resistance, stopping time, coalescence and global footprint. The three-layer stratigraphy (core, critical boundary, periphery) provides a coherent framework to interpret these phenomena. Future work may aim to rigorously formalize these heuristic results and extend the analysis to nonlinear generalizations.

Code and Data

The Python code for the experiments is available on GitHub: <https://github.com/aniskh/sufes>

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